

Automatic Music Transcription

A brief introduction featuring open questions and challenges

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Abstract

Automatic Music Transcription (AMT) is a process that involves the transformation of musical audio into notated musical symbols. Our exploration has delineated the history of AMT and emphasized recent breakthroughs brought about by the application of transformer models and the increased availability of training data. Furthermore, it yielded that the challenge of transitioning from piano roll representations to traditional sheet music notation is currently under-examined. Our examination of the field’s current landscape has identified several promising directions for future research. Notably, these avenues include the development of benchmarks prioritizing perceptual authenticity, the expansion of datasets to enhance the comprehensiveness of training, and the infusion of insights from auditory cognition. Of particular interest is the integration of a musical language model into the transcription process, which holds the potential of improving AMT accuracy and versatility. The findings presented in this essay paint a coarse picture of the current state of AMT and offer informed suggestions for future investigations.

1 Introduction

Musical notation is the main reason we have access to thousands of pieces of music created by people who lived in a time before acoustic signals could simply be recorded and played back at the tap of a button. In order to recreate the sound of a piece in the absence of its original performer, the music had to be transcribed into written instructions and passed on to someone who can interpret these instructions. Certainly, a strong impetus behind the practice of music transcription was to facilitate synchronized performances of intricate compositions by multiple musicians. This removed the necessity for each performer to commit the entire piece to memory or listen to it in its entirety before executing it. A welcome side effect of having these transcriptions, is, that even generations later, they afford glimpses into facets of past cultures which very likely carried emotional significance at their time of creation. Without the transcription into musical notation, this emotionally significant connection to past cultures could have been, quite literally, gone with the wind.

Most people are capable of intuitive acoustic engagement with music. Here, this means they can track and memorize individual melodies, hum along more or less accurately, follow rhythms, tell voices apart, and have a general sense of whether overlapping notes are consonant or dissonant. Even so, without extensive training or unusual natural ability, untrained listeners and even a good proportion of trained musicians would not be able to *accurately* identify and transcribe every single pitch making up a moderately complex piece of music without reference. Consequently, musical notation continues to be invaluable for those interested in performing or studying others' compositions, yet it can only be efficiently created by individuals with substantial musical training or innate talent.

The process of encoding a musical sequence into visual symbols, akin to how speech can be represented through sequences of letters, is referred to as *music transcription*. Extending this concept, *Automatic Music Transcription* encompasses the same process, with the added feature that the transcription can be carried out from start to finish without requiring additional human intervention. The evident value of such a system for purposes ranging from musical education, preservation, performance, and distribution, along with the inherent commercial appeal tied to its utility, has ignited both academic and commercial interest.

Music transcription, much like speech recognition, encounters growing complexity as the number of overlapping sources in a recording multiplies. A musical composition with overlapping notes, regardless of the number of sources involved, is termed "polyphonic." Given that a substantial portion of music falls into the polyphonic category, an AMT system of the magnitude envisioned in this context should be proficient in managing polyphony and other intricacies typical of real-world musical recordings.

The aim of the present work is twofold. First, we intend to introduce the reader to the field of AMT, including a short trace of its history as well as a presentation of the current state-of-the-art. Secondly, we would like to present a selection of open questions which could serve as fertile ground for a short series of scientific investigations pursued under the interdisciplinary umbrella of cognitive science.

2 An abbreviated history of AMT

One of the first exhaustive attempts at polyphonic music transcription using computers has been documented in Moorer's 1975 dissertation. In his dissertation, he used an array of signal processing techniques in order to successfully create automatic transcriptions of a 4-bar violin duet as well as a 4-bar guitar duet. In order to achieve success, Moorer placed some limitations on the source audio that his system was supposed to transcribe. AMT research that followed did limit source audio in a similar fashion. These limitations typically involved constraining the number of voices, ensuring that overlapping notes were not harmonically related, excluding percussive sounds entirely, fixing note lengths

at specific durations, disregarding slides, trills, or other ornaments, maintaining a consistent tempo, and exclusively featuring specific instruments or synthetic sound sources. Moorer’s adherence to these constraints, as documented in his dissertation, undoubtedly constrained the practical utility of his transcription system [1].

While recognizing the commendable achievements within these specific musical transcription goals, it is worth noting that their applicability remains confined. This constraint encourages the exploration of alternative signal processing techniques, pattern recognition systems, and fresh insights rooted in auditory cognition, potentially advancing the field of AMT.

There are good reasons why AMT ambitions have been curbed in the way delineated above. Around 50 years of research have demonstrated that AMT, in the general sense envisioned here, is remarkably difficult. By the time the first truly exhaustive overview of AMT was written, the authors concluded “[the] state-of-the-art music transcription systems are still clearly inferior to skilled human musicians in accuracy and flexibility. That is, a reliable general-purpose transcription system does not exist at the present time.” [2] (p.7). While in their overview, data-driven methods like Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are treated as a side note among many other, more robust and interpretable signal-processing techniques, the authors, perhaps, could not anticipate the on-going big-data-induced ANN revolution and hype that characterized the 16 years that followed. One of the reasons why the ANNs were treated as such in [2] could be their reliance on large amounts of data and processing power. Both were limited in 2006 and would thus only amount to few studies on the applicability of ANNs to AMT.

In 2019, separated by 12 years of what has been in jest referred to as ANN “revolution” here, another major AMT overview has been published by [3]. Although of smaller scale than Klapuri’s work, the authors manage to provide a concise introduction to the field of AMT, incorporating recent advancements and open challenges. In their eyes, contemporary state-of-the-art AMT performance had been set by Google Brain’s Onsets and Frames Network. The network is capable of transcribing polyphonic piano music with, at the time of publication, unprecedented accuracy [4].

Since then, a new kind of generative neural network architecture, the transformer, has attracted considerable attention for its effectiveness in sequence-to-sequence tasks such as natural language processing [5]. This attention is reflected by public interest in the present day’s AI hot topic: large language models that are built on the Generative Pre-Trained *Transformer* architecture. AMT researchers were quick to pick up on the potential benefits of transformers for their field of inquiry. Thus, studies pioneering the applicability of transformers to melody extraction [6] and piano transcription with note velocity [7] have already been published. However, a still often cited limitation of ANN-based AMT is the scarcity of annotated datasets [3].

3 MT3 : The State of the Art

Consequently, the most successful AMT system so far has focused on overcoming the limitations posed by data scarcity. Its key contributions have not only pushed the state-of-the-art for the transcription of one particular instrument. Instead, it succeeded at a much more complicated task referred to as “Multi-Task Multitrack Music Transcription” (MT3) by the original authors [8]. It involves the simultaneous transcription of multiple instruments (Multitrack) for different types of source audio, i.e. , genres (Multi-Task) as depicted in Fig. 1.

Named after the task it is intended to accomplish, MT3 outperforms the models featured in reference studies on all metrics (Frame F1, Onset F1, Onset+Offset F1) across all datasets (MAESTRO, Cerberus4, Guitarset, MusicNet, Slakh2100, URMP), often by a significant margin (Table 1). For an explanation of these metrics and datasets, the reader is referred to [8].

Figure 1: ”MT3 is capable of transcribing an arbitrary number of instruments from raw audio spectrograms. Shown here are real 4-second audio clips, piano rolls reconstructed from the model’s tokenized output, and the corresponding instrument labels. Note that in some cases, multiple notes predicted from a monophonic instrument (such as clarinet or French horn) reflect an ensemble containing multiple players of that instrument.”

Note. Adapted from Josh Gardner et al. *MT3: Multi-Task Multitrack Music Transcription*. arXiv:2111.03017 [cs, eess]. Mar. 2022. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2111.03017> (visited on 10/26/2023)

Model	MAESTRO	Cerberus4	GuitarSet	MusicNet	Slakh2100	URMP
<i>Frame F1</i>						
Hawthorne et al. (2021)	0.66	–	–	–	–	–
Manilow et al. (2020)	–	0.63	0.54	–	–	–
Cheuk et al. (2021)	–	–	–	0.48	–	–
Melodyne	0.41	0.39	0.62	0.13	0.47	0.30
MT3 (single dataset)	0.88	0.85	0.82	0.60	0.78	0.49
MT3 (mixture)	0.86	0.87	0.89	0.68	0.79	0.83
<i>Onset F1</i>						
Hawthorne et al. (2021)	0.96	–	–	–	–	–
Manilow et al. (2020)	–	0.67	0.16	–	–	–
Cheuk et al. (2021)	–	–	–	0.29	–	–
Melodyne	0.52	0.24	0.28	0.04	0.30	0.09
MT3 (single dataset)	0.96	0.89	0.83	0.39	0.76	0.40
MT3 (mixture)	0.95	0.92	0.90	0.50	0.76	0.77
<i>Onset+Offset F1</i>						
Hawthorne et al. (2021)	0.84	–	–	–	–	–
Manilow et al. (2020)	–	0.37	0.08	–	–	–
Cheuk et al. (2021)	–	–	–	0.11	–	–
Melodyne	0.06	0.07	0.13	0.01	0.10	0.04
MT3 (single dataset)	0.84	0.76	0.65	0.21	0.57	0.16
MT3 (mixture)	0.80	0.80	0.78	0.33	0.57	0.58
Mixture ($\Delta\%$)	-5.3	+5.2	+19.5	+54.0	+0.1	+263

Table 1: ”Transcription F1 scores for Frame, Onset, and Onset+Offset metrics defined [in [8]]. Across all metrics and all datasets, MT3 consistently outperforms the baseline systems it’s being compared against. Dataset mixing during training (“mixture”), specifically, shows a large performance increase over single dataset training, especially for low-resource datasets like GuitarSet, MusicNet, and URMP. Percent increase over single-dataset training for Onset+Offset F1 is shown in the last row.”

Note. Adapted from Josh Gardner et al. *MT3: Multi-Task Multitrack Music Transcription*. arXiv:2111.03017 [cs, eess]. Mar. 2022. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2111.03017> (visited on 10/26/2023)

To the best of the authors knowledge, MT3 is the most successful rendition of a general-purpose AMT system to date and should thus serve as a baseline for future work. This success has been achieved by a few innovations in the approach to training the AMT system. First, the authors overcame the problem associated with data scarcity for low-resource datasets like GuitarSet (3h) and URMP (1.3h) by combining all datasets into one large and mixed dataset. The performance gains by addressing data scarcity are particularly salient in the comparison between MT3 (single dataset) and MT3 (mixture) scores for the URMP dataset (Table 1). Second, they successfully integrated an off-the-shelf transformer architecture into their AMT system devised by previous authors (Raffel et al. 2019, as cited in [8]). As mentioned above, this is a key contribution since transformers boast outstanding performance in sequence-to-sequence tasks [5]. Third, they found a suitable vocabulary as model output that generalizes well across all datasets. It includes tokens encoding *instrument type*, *note*, *“on/off”-signals*, *absolute time*, *percussion onset*, *End Tie Section* and *End of Sequence*.

Figure 2: Piano roll output of MT3 based on the wave audio of a particular song from a dataset featuring multiple instruments. The left side depicts the identity of MIDI pitches displayed as piano keys. Height of the colored bars indicates the pitch or note. The length of the bars indicates note duration. Black lines demarcate segments which were consecutively fed into the model. One segment lasts 2048 ms. TP (blue): True Positive, FN (green): False Negative, FP (red): False Positive

Note. Adapted from Josh Gardner et al. *MT3: Multi-Task Multitrack Music Transcription*. arXiv:2111.03017 [cs, eess]. Mar. 2022. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2111.03017> (visited on 10/26/2023)

With these three innovations, MT3 comprises a general-purpose AMT system jointly trained on six prominent but varied datasets, totaling around 1750 h of audio, using a transformer architecture with 60 million parameters capable of identifying pitch, note on/offsets and instrument type with unprecedented accuracy across all datasets.

3.1 MT3 Limitations

MT3 performs reasonably well at AMT across genres present in the dataset. This begs the question of how well it generalizes to other genres that have not been featured in the training data. Results of “leave-one-dataset-out” experiments, where the authors excluded individual datasets from training, suggest that MT3’s performance on evaluation datasets relies on the presence of training data from the same dataset. In the words of the authors, this “[highlights] the resource-constrained nature of the available music transcription datasets even when combined. For example, the Slakh2100 + Cerberus4 combination is the only dataset [...] that contains bass and synthesizer; without training on those datasets, the model is unable to learn to identify these instruments.” [8]. Still, MT3 is capable of transcribing some novel data with respectable accuracy, as demonstrated on their supplementary website.¹

¹<https://storage.googleapis.com/mt3/index.html>

4 Open Questions and Challenges

4.1 Defining AMT Goals and Benchmarks

The relative improvement of MT3 compared to its predecessors is undeniable. Likewise, insofar as the examples provided by [8] are representative of the overall transcription quality, transcription mistakes do not appear to be particularly frequent or grave. Even so, we share the author’s intuition that, despite their progress, AMT has not been *solved*. This raises the question: What would it mean to “solve” AMT? Answering it involves deciding on specific transcription goals and evaluation metrics. For example, if the end goal is merely the estimation of pitches at the right times, Onset/Offset F1 may be a sufficiently suitable measure. Of course, the rendition of the correct pitch at the right time is not all there is to extract from musical recordings. Information about the loudness of individual notes may also be worth preserving during transcription. For instruments with soft note onsets and offsets, using Onset/Offset F1 as a metric may even skew the evaluation towards negative results. Whichever musical parameters are transcribed, evaluation metrics are deployed, or accuracy level is set as bar for success; it should correspond closely to the consensus of human expert judges. Thus, the refinement of transcription metrics and its formalization for automatic evaluation must still be addressed by AMT researchers.

4.2 Translation from MIDI-like data to Sheet Music

So far, we have remained silent with regard to a critical processing step of what would constitute a *complete* AMT pipeline: the generation of sheet music. AMT systems such as MT3 or any of the others mentioned here only create piano roll output of the kind depicted in Fig. 2. The generation of sheet music comes with its own set of problems, including but not limited to beat tracking, meter estimation, identifying ornamental markings, and correctly displaying multiple voices on one staff. To the best of the author’s knowledge, there is **no** academic work published in any of the common outlets, addressing the quality of current means for translating MIDI-like data into sheet music.

4.3 The creation of a Large Dataset

Platforms like MuseScore, host a tremendous amount Music XML files, which represent sheet music in a markup language. Music XML can be converted into MIDI files. MIDI files, in turn, can be rendered as high quality audio, provided high-end virtual instruments are used for the rendition. The musical notations with licenses for fair use hosted by MuseScore or other platforms thus provide the grounds for the generation of large amounts of correctly annotated musical audio. This would enable the generation of a dataset that we estimate to exceed the one used in MT3 or related systems by at least one order of magnitude in size. The creation of such a dataset by itself could thus stand alone as an academic contribution to the field of AMT.

4.4 Inclusion of Insights from Auditory Cognition

Another approach to AMT which has not been extensively explored so far, is the integration of insights from musical cognition into transcription pipelines. Research on patients with brain damage that resulted in the loss of specific musical abilities suggests that there are multiple, discernible modules for musical processing. Among others, these include modules for the analysis of acoustics, rhythm, meter, contour and intervals, as well as a musical lexicon. [9]. Studying these models and finding ways to integrate them into AMT pipelines could prove fruitful. For example, the "musical lexicon" mentioned in [9] might be implemented as a musical language model based on adjacent fields at the intersection between machine learning and music. A musical language model could be used to increase the confidence of transcriptions, as suggested in [3]. This may be particularly beneficial for cases in which source audio quality is low. Lastly, investigations into the neural processing mechanisms underlying the exceptional pitch perception of people with an ability referred to as *absolute* or *perfect* pitch could provide further inspiration for AMT researchers and engineers as well.

5 Conclusion

After more than 50 years since the advent of the field, recent successes, particularly in the case of MT3, serve as compelling proof of concept for the development of a general-purpose automatic music transcription system. These advancements underscore the importance of addressing the scarcity of annotated datasets, which has been a frequently noted constraint in previous studies. Despite the remarkable achievements, the conversion of piano roll representations into sheet music and the establishment of suitable benchmarks with perceptual authenticity remain open challenges, raising a multitude of questions paving the way for multiple interdisciplinary investigations to be conducted in the future.

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